

Optimization of the membrane electrode assembly for an alkaline water electrolyser based on the catalyst-coated membrane

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Preparation of catalyst coated membrane electrode assembly optimised.
- Bottle-neck of the catalyst coated membrane determined.
- Excellent stability achieved during 140 h test at 250 mA cm⁻².

ABSTRACT

This study deals with the preparation and characterisation of catalyst-coated membranes for an alkaline water electrolysis process. For this purpose, a chloromethylated anion-selective block copolymer of styrene-ethylene-butylene-styrene with 1,4-diazabicyclo[2.2.2]octane functional groups was used both as an alkaline polymer electrolyte membrane and as an ionomer binder. Non-PGM catalysts (platinum group metals), specifically NiCo₂O₄ and NiFe₂O₄, were used on the anode and cathode side of the membrane, respectively. Air-brush deposition or computer-controlled ultrasonic dispersion of the catalytic ink were used to deposit the catalyst layers. The influence of the composition of the catalyst layer on its stability and the resulting electrolysis cell performance was investigated under typical membrane alkaline water electrolysis conditions (1–15 wt.% KOH, 45 °C). The optimal catalyst-to-binder ratio in the catalyst layer was identified as 93/7 using a catalyst loading of 2.5 mg cm⁻² on each side of the membrane. The membrane electrode assembly prepared under optimal conditions showed high stability over 140 h at a current density of 250 mA cm⁻². At this current load, the cell exhibited a voltage of 2.025 ± 0.010 V. The increase in cell voltage observed during the stability test did not exceed 1 μV h⁻¹.

1. Introduction

Alkaline water electrolysis (AWE) represents a mature and relatively cost-effective technology for hydrogen production from renewable energy sources. Traditional technology has been based for more than a century on the use of a porous diaphragm-type separator [1]. The main disadvantage of this approach is in the necessity to operate highly concentrated KOH solutions as a liquid electrolyte with a negative impact on the flexibility of the process. At the same time, the use of a relatively thick diaphragm increases cell resistance [2]. It also represents a safety issue for low-capacity distributed hydrogen production systems. Furthermore, the porous structure of the separator prevents the mixing of gases produced in the individual electrode compartments [3]. This is especially important when operating the cell under high and/or asymmetric pressure. Therefore, currently significant effort is directed

towards the development of a new generation of AWE using a dense anion-selective polymer electrolyte (MAWE) [4]. The use of an anion-selective polymer electrolyte leads to a cell design similar to that of proton exchange membrane (PEM) water electrolysis, while retaining the advantage of an alkaline environment, i.e. the use of economically viable materials. This approach allows one to reduce separator thickness [5], while elevated and/or asymmetric pressure can be applied to the cell [6]. The main obstacle, however, is the limited stability of currently available anion-exchange membranes in an alkaline environment at elevated temperatures [7–9].

One of the key advantages of MAWE compared to traditional AWE technology is expected to be the utilisation of deionised water as a circulating medium instead of a KOH solution [10]. In such an arrangement, however, sufficiently intensive ionic contact between the catalyst layer and the membrane separator is a key aspect. This problem

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can be solved using a membrane electrode assembly (MEA) prepared by applying the catalyst directly on the membrane surface. This approach entails using a catalyst coated membrane (CCM) [11]. A second approach, involving a catalyst coated substrate (CCS), consists in depositing a catalyst layer on the porous transport layer (PTL) based on a material with high electronic conductivity [12]. The advantage of the latter method is the good electronic contact of the catalyst layer with the current feeder. However, it is achieved at the expense of the ionic contact with the membrane.

In the case of the CCS approach, inert polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) is usually used as the binder of the catalyst layer [13–16]. This is mainly due to the absence of a sufficiently stable ionomer suitable for the role of the catalyst layer binder and the high chemical stability of PTFE. However, PTFE solely acts as a catalyst binder, only ensuring the mechanical stability of the catalyst layer. It does not possess the required ionic conductivity. Due to this, a KOH solution at concentrations ranging from 0.1 to 2.35 mol dm⁻³ [13–15,17–20] has to be used as a circulating medium to ensure ionic conductivity in the structure of the catalyst layer. Moreover, PTFE has a strongly hydrophobic character and, as such, does not facilitate the removal of gasses from the catalyst layer [18]. Thus, the binder content has to be optimised to achieve the best cell performance. The studies performed have shown that more than 20 wt.% of binder in the catalyst layer causes partial blockage of the catalyst surface and thus deterioration of cell performance [15]. The best results were observed for 10 wt.% of PTFE binder on both the cathode and the anode side [13,14,17].

In the case of CCM, the anion-selective binder of the catalyst layer represents the only viable option. This is due to (i) limited compatibility of PTFE and the polymer of the anion-selective membrane, but mainly due to the fact that (ii) the PTFE-bonded catalyst layer needs to be heat treated after its deposition at a temperature above 300 °C [21] to ensure formation of the continuous web of the PTFE binder, guaranteeing mechanical stability of the layer. However, at such high temperatures, the anion-selective polymer electrolyte membrane is not stable. Regarding the use of CCMs for MAWE, only a limited number of studies have been published up to now. They focus both on the use of different types of commercially available [22–26] as well as experimental membranes or ionomers [5,11,24,27–31]. Both PGM [23–25,30–32] and non-PGM catalysts [5,11,22,27–29] are used. The relatively low publishing activity in this field is primarily caused by the limited availability of anion-selective polymer materials suitable for use as the separator and binder in an alkaline environment. But, recently, great deal of efforts has been made to develop AEMs with high hydroxide conductivity, good chemical/thermal/mechanical stability and low cost [33]. For quaternary ammonium type of AAEM, its degradation mechanisms have been well understood. The insufficient stability against hydroxide attack due to nucleophilic substitution, Hofmann and/or E1 elimination reaction forced the development of novel AEMs [34]. The cation chemical stability could be improved by adding large functional or electron-donating groups. N-alicyclic quaternary ammonium represents a kind of competitive substitute for common quaternary ammonium because of the larger steric hindrance [35]. At the same time, electron-donating groups (e.g. methoxy groups) help protect the cation group from OH- attack [36]. For example, piperidinium functional groups show high hydroxide conductivity and stability [37,38]. Non-ammonium cation groups, such as imidazolium and guanidinium, have also attracted attention. It is because their resonant structures can in theory outperform quaternary ammonium. Ionically conductive inorganic compounds, such as layered double hydroxides (LDHs), could be used because of their high stability in alkaline media. If incorporated and fixed in a chemically robust polymer matrix, LDH may lead to the formation of AAEMs with both good conductivity and high stability [39]. Besides the development of new AEMs, the influence of the working environment was studied [40]. It was found out, that the stability can be improved with sufficient level of hydration even in concentrated KOH solution at elevated temperature, because the water molecules limit the

distance the hydroxide ions may approach to the functional group. So, novel AEMs materials are being developed. They are, however, not easily available and usually still do not fulfil the durability requirement in an operating electrolysis cell [41].

Using an anion-selective binder enables a decrease in the KOH concentration in the liquid electrolyte, since the binder can, to a certain extent, ensure ionic contact between the catalyst forming the catalyst layer and the membrane [42]. The CCM approach incurs another important advantage over CCS. Namely, close contact between the catalyst layer and the membrane. This aspect becomes extremely important when there is a decrease in KOH concentration, especially when deionised water is used as the circulating medium. It also leads to improved utilisation of the catalyst [43], the catalyst layer being thinner than in the case of CCS [44–46]. Therefore, the usual concentration range of KOH/NaOH in a liquid electrolyte can be reduced to 0–1 mol dm⁻³ [47,48]. The effect of the amount of binder also needs to be monitored since it must ensure the mechanical stability of the catalyst layer, provide a conductive pathway for the OH- ions and at the same time not disturb the electronic contact between the catalyst particles. The optimal amount was found to range between 5 and 20 wt.% [21,23,49]. 5 wt.% of ionomer was found to be the minimal amount to meet the stability requirements. The decrease in charge-transfer resistance of the electrode reactions was observed during the increase in the binder content to up to 20 wt.% of binder in the layer. This was attributed to the increase in the number of secondary pores in the layer, which improves the transport of reactants to the active site of the catalyst [23]. This seems to be caused by an agglomeration of the catalyst to form larger agglomerates, creating a larger pore structure between them. Exceeding the optimal level of the binder leads to a blockage in the porous structure. Generally, there are several ways of preparing CCMs, such as: decal [47,48], doctor blade [50], screen printing [51] and direct spray method, the last mentioned being used most commonly [26,52,53].

However, despite all the advances achieved recently, when using deionised water as the circulating medium, the performance of the electrolysis is still rather low [5,28,30] compared to the use of KOH solution as an electrolyte [23,30]. Therefore, more effort is needed to understand the causes of this situation in their entire complexity in order to propose suitable solutions.

The target of this study is to extend the knowledge reported in our previous paper [11], where the potential of the CCM approach to decrease the catalyst load to 2.5 mg cm⁻², while maintaining the performance of the MAWE, was reported. In the present work, attention is paid to a thorough optimisation of the CCM preparation method with respect to the catalyst/binder ratio (CBR). The information obtained facilitates a deeper understanding of the interaction between the binder and catalyst, which further development in this field requires. At the same time, CCM production steps, such as functionalisation, are further optimised. The results achieved confirm that CCMs with optimised catalyst layers represent a promising path to improve MAWE technology.

2. Experimental part

2.1. Materials

Polystyrene-*block*-poly(ethylene-*ran*-butylene)-*block*-polystyrene (PSEBS) (0.21 butylene, 0.67 ethylene, 0.12 styrene), dimethoxy-methane DMOM (≥99%), phosphorous chloride (PCl₃) (99%) and 1,4-diazabicyclo[2.2.2]octane (DABCO) (≥99%) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich, Czech Republic. Zinc chloride anhydrous (ZnCl₂) (>99%) was obtained from Lachema, Czech Republic. Chloroform (p.a), toluene (p.a) and ethanol (technical grade) were purchased from Lach-Ner, Czech Republic.

The nickel nitrate hexahydrate Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (≥99%), iron chloride FeCl₃ (≥98%) and sodium hydroxide NaOH (99%) used for catalyst preparation were obtained from PENTA, Czech Republic. Cobalt nitrate

hexahydrate $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\geq 99\%$) originates from LachNer, Czech Republic.

The electrodes were prepared from Ni foam (INCO Advanced Technology Materials (Dalian) Co., Ltd). The liquid electrolyte was prepared from potassium hydroxide KOH (85%, PENTA, Czech Republic).

2.2. Catalyst preparation

A detailed description of the preparation method of non-precious catalysts is provided elsewhere [18,54]. Just a brief summary is given here. The NiCo_2O_4 anode catalyst was prepared from a stoichiometric amount of $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2.91 g) and $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1.45 g) mixed with 150 ml of deionised water and stirred for 15 min with a magnetic stirrer. An aqueous solution of 2 mol dm^{-3} of NaOH was added while stirring until the pH exceeded 12 and a black precipitate formed. The precipitate was filtered, washed thoroughly with deionised water and dried at $80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The last step was calcination at $325\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 4 h in air atmosphere with a temperature ramp of $4\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ per minute. The NiFe_2O_4 cathode catalyst was prepared using a procedure analogous to that for NiCo_2O_4 . $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were dissolved and precipitated. Calcination took place at $475\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 4 h in an air atmosphere.

2.3. Synthesis of polymer materials

A detailed procedure of membrane synthesis and subsequent characterisation is described elsewhere [55]. Briefly, PSEBS was dissolved in chloroform to obtain a 5 wt.% solution. An in-situ chlorinating agent was prepared in the PSEBS solution by adding 10.5 g of dimethoxy-methane, ZnCl_2 and PCl_3 . The mixture was stirred until it was completely dissolved or a time of 1 h was reached. In the latter case, a fine dispersion was formed. Isolation of the chloromethylated PSEBS (PSEBS-CM) was performed by precipitation into ethanol followed by filtration. In the next step, the dry polymer was dissolved in chloroform. The membrane was prepared by casting a thin film of the resulting solution and evaporating the solvent at room temperature. Quaternisation was performed by immersing the membrane in a 10 wt.% DABCO solution in ethanol at room temperature for 72 h. The average thickness of the dry cast membrane without functional groups was $110\text{ }\mu\text{m}$, that of the dry functionalised membrane was $170\text{ }\mu\text{m}$.

2.4. Membrane pre-treatment and MEA preparation

Prior to use, the membranes were activated and converted into a Cl⁻ cycle. The activation process consisted of immersing the membrane in solutions alternating between low and high pH at $25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The first step in this process was immersion of the membrane in 100 ml of 0.1 mol dm^{-3} NaOH solution for 2 h. This was followed by removing the membrane from the solution, rinsing it with deionised water (conductivity $< 0.5\text{ }\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$) and immersing it in 100 ml of a 0.1 mol dm^{-3} HCl solution for 24 h. The activated membranes were stored in deionised water.

The catalyst ink was prepared by mixing the catalyst powder with a 5 wt.% solution of PSEBS-CM binder in chloroform. Chloroform was used as a dispersant. Different ratios of catalyst and polymer binder (CBR – catalyst/binder ratio) were studied in the range of 50/50 to 98/2. In order to make the figures clear to the reader, only selected CBRs (50/50, 90/10, 93/7) are presented in this study. The CBRs with binder content less than 7% were not mechanically stable. Thus, their characteristics are not presented here. The catalyst ink was homogenised in an ultrasonic bath for 30 min. Consequently, it was applied to an activated PSEBS-CM-DABCO membrane with an active area of $2 \times 2\text{ cm}^2$. The ink application was performed by air-brush deposition or computer-controlled ultrasonic dispersion deposition (hereinafter referred to as CNC). During deposition, the membrane was kept at a temperature of $50\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to accelerate solvent evaporation. After application of the catalyst layer (2.5 mg cm^{-2} of catalyst, different amount of PSEBS-CM polymer binder), the membranes were immersed in a 10 wt.% solution of DABCO

in ethanol at $25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h to functionalise the binder in the catalyst layer. After removal from the solution, the membranes were rinsed with deionised water and immersed in 1 mol dm^{-3} NaOH solution for 24 h and thus transferred to the OH⁻ form.

2.5. Conductivity of the catalyst powders

The conductivity of the catalyst powders was determined by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy. A small amount of the catalyst was inserted into the non-conductive polyethylene cell, between two copper pistons, and its thickness was measured by means of a micrometre. The cell was always tightened with a torque screwdriver to torque 20 cN m to ensure reproducible compression of the layers. This measurement was repeated six times. Each time, more catalyst was added to the cell and the dependence of the resistance (ohm) on the thickness of the layer (mm) was measured. The conductivity was calculated from the linear slope of the dependence and cross-section area of the cell (A , mm^2).

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{A \times \text{slope}} \times 1000 [\text{S m}^{-1}]$$

A programmable LCR bridge HAMEG HM8118 (ROHDE & SCHWARZ) was used to record the resistance values for the signal frequency range of 100 Hz–200 kHz. The maximum amplitude of the perturbing voltage signal used was 50 mV.

2.6. Catalyst layer conductivity determination

A catalyst layer with CBR 50/50 and 80/20 was deposited by air-brush on the inert solid substrate with a dimension of $5 \times 1\text{ cm}^2$. The catalyst layer was then removed from the substrate, and the binder in the layer was functionalised as described above. Before measurement, the sample was placed in 0.1 mol dm^{-3} NaOH solution to equilibrate the sample in the OH⁻ cycle. The ionic conductivity was measured in the transverse direction in the cell with a circular active area of 15.7 mm^2 using mercury electrodes and Pt wires as contacts at laboratory temperature. A programmable LCR bridge HAMEG HM8118 (ROHDE & SCHWARZ) was used to record the resistance value of the catalyst layer in the frequency range of 200 kHz–20 Hz. The maximum amplitude of the perturbing signal used was 50 mV. The ionic conductivity of the catalyst layers was calculated from the resistivity according to the formula $\sigma = \frac{d}{R \times S}$, where σ represents the ionic conductivity [S m^{-1}], d corresponds to the thickness of the measured sample [m], R is the measured resistance [Ω] and S stands for an area of the sample [m^2]. The sample conductivity was first measured prior to functionalisation, which corresponds to the electric conductivity of the catalyst phase in the layer. After that, the sample was functionalised and the measurement was repeated. At this time, the value obtained corresponds to the combined electric and ionic conductivity.

2.7. MEA characterisation

The morphology of the prepared catalyst layers was investigated using a Hitachi S4700 scanning electron microscope (SEM) (Hitachi, Japan). The samples were placed on an aluminium pad. Double-sided carbon adhesive tape was used to fix them in position. To obtain a cross-section, the dry sample was cut using a scalpel. The samples were coated with a conductive Au/Pd layer approximately 20 nm thick by vacuum sputtering.

Alkaline electrolysis of water was performed in a laboratory test station. Nickel foam electrodes with dimensions $2 \times 2\text{ cm}^2$ were pressed directly on to the catalyst layers deposited on the membrane surface. The MEA was placed in an electrolysis cell made of polyether-etherketone (PEEK). A GORE GR 05 Teflon (WL Gore & Associates Inc.) sealing and gold-plated nickel current feeders were used. The KOH

solution (1, 5, 10, or 15 wt.%) was used as a circulating liquid electrolyte. A flow rate of 5 ml min^{-1} and temperature of 45°C were selected. A Statron 3251.1 laboratory power supply (Statron Gerätetechnik, Germany) was used to apply the gradually increasing cell voltage. A voltage range of 1.5–2.0 V was studied using 0.05 V steps. The corresponding current was recorded.

A long-term stability test was performed at a constant current load of 250 mA cm^{-2} using a liquid electrolyte concentration of 10 wt.% KOH and a temperature of 45°C . Simultaneously with MAWE testing, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy was recorded using a Solartron SI1250 frequency analyzer in connection with a Solartron SI1287 electrochemical interface. The impedance spectra were recorded at cell voltages of 0, 1.5 and 1.8 V. The maximum amplitude of the perturbing signal used was 10 mV. Measurements at 0 V were performed in a frequency range of 65 kHz–100 Hz, while impedance spectra measured at 1.5 and 1.8 V were performed in a frequency range 65 kHz - 0.1 Hz. The equivalent circuit used to evaluate the parameters of the electrolysis cell is shown in Fig. 1. The circuit was composed of L (H) (inductance of connecting cables), R_s (Ω) (system resistivity), R_p (Ω) (polarisation resistance) and CPE (constant phase element).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Catalyst/binder ratio

To evaluate the effect of the binder content in the catalyst layer on its compactness as well as on the performance of the MEA, we studied different CBRs. In Fig. 2A MAWE load curves are compared for two concentrations of potassium hydroxide (1 and 15 wt.%) and for different CBRs (50/50, 90/10 and 93/7). With increasing electrolyte concentration, the electrochemical performance of all MEAs improves due to the higher concentration of OH^- ions present in the system, leading to improved ionic contact within the catalyst layer, between the catalyst layer and the membrane, and of the membrane itself. The reason is that the mobility of OH^- ions in the ionomer is not as high as it is in the case of H^+ ions in the PEM system. The KOH solution thus provides additional OH^- conducting pathways in the catalyst layer. With increasing KOH concentration in the environment, Donnan exclusion is also overcome, and excessive OH^- ions, together with co-ions can penetrate into the bulk of the anion-selective polymer materials, thus resulting in an increase in the electrolyte conductivity of the anion-selective polymer. The dependence of cell performance on KOH concentration is not linear, as it may appear in Fig. 2A. The performance improvement is more progressive in a lower concentration range (e.g., between 5 and 10 wt.% KOH). With increasing KOH concentration, its effect gradually diminishes (see Fig. S1 – S3 in Supporting information (SI)).

The impact of CBR on the MEA performance provides an interesting insight into the role of the polymer binder in the catalyst layer. Within the CBR range shown in Fig. 2A, decreasing the content of the binder resulted in an improvement in MEA performance. Comparing the current densities reached in 15 wt.% KOH at 2 V, 50/50 CBR achieved 130 mA cm^{-2} , 90/10 CBR achieved 156 mA cm^{-2} and 93/7 CBR achieved 183 mA cm^{-2} . For 1 wt.% KOH, these current densities are 52, 66 and 79 mA cm^{-2} , respectively.

To attain a deeper understanding of the observations made, the system resistivity (R_s) and polarisation (R_p) resistances were evaluated

from the EIS recorded and are summarised for the different concentrations of KOH and CBRs in Fig. 2B and C (measured spectra are shown in Fig. S4 – S7 in SI). Generally, R_s is related to the ohmic resistivity of the current collectors, the catalyst layer, the electrolyte, and the contact resistance between the catalyst layer and the electrolyte. As in an ideal case all cell components, except the catalyst layer, are the same for all the experiments shown, any differences observed can thus be attributed to the different CBRs. Here, the decrease in R_s between 50/50 and 93/7 CBRs in 1 wt.% KOH reaches approximately 28%, while in 15 wt.% KOH the decrease is about 23%. The close values of the relative change in R_s confirm the behaviour of the catalyst layer as slightly dependent on the liquid electrolyte concentration. However, a more surprising observation is the increasing R_s value with increasing content of ionomer binder in the catalyst layer. This could be explained by the different thicknesses of the catalyst layers with different CBRs. The overall thickness of the two catalyst layers (without membrane) in the dry state are $106 \mu\text{m}$ for 50/50 and $73 \mu\text{m}$ for 93/7, see Fig. 2D and E. This is clearly caused by an increased amount of ionomer in the catalytic layer at CBR 50/50 (catalyst loading the same). An additional aspect, however, is the layer thickness in the wet state. For CBR 50/50 it reached $185 \mu\text{m}$, compared to only $96 \mu\text{m}$ for 93/7 CBR. This important difference is predominantly caused by swelling of the ionomer. It results, not only in increased thickness of the layer, but also in an important increase in the distance between the catalyst particles in the catalyst layer. For this reason, it is highly probable that, for CBR 50/50, the conductivity of the layer in the swollen state solely corresponds to the ionic conductivity of the catalyst layer itself. This also explains the observed polarisation resistances of the MEA during electrolysis discussed later in the text. Insufficient electronic contact between catalyst particles across the layer may also explain the sensitivity to the content of the ionomer and, to a certain extent, the lower performance of CCM over CCS in the case of KOH of sufficient concentration [11].

Similar to R_s , the R_{p1} values are also commonly higher for CBR 50/50 compared to 93/7. However, the R_{p2} values exhibit different behaviour. Whereas at a KOH concentration of 1 wt.% the R_{p2} value shows a minimum for CBR 90/10, at 15 wt.% the R_{p2} values increase with the CBR. Since R_{p1} shows a significantly higher value than R_{p2} , these results are fully in line with the load curves shown in Fig. 2A. However, to understand the behaviour observed, additional information is needed.

The morphology of the cross-section of the catalyst layer was studied by SEM. Fig. 2D and E shows corresponding photographs of the CCM with CBR values of 50/50 and 93/7. These pictures confirm that the 50/50 CBR catalyst layer is highly compact and shows no visual differences in morphology compared to the bulk membrane. In contrast, 93/7 CBR provides distinguishable porous catalyst layers with good adhesion to the membrane surface. The thickness of these layers ranges from 30 to $60 \mu\text{m}$ for the anode and cathode, respectively. Compared to the swollen state, in the case of CBR 50/50, the increase in thickness of the catalyst layer is around 43%. In the case of CBR 93/7 the situation is different and the increase in thickness of the catalyst layer related to the swelling of the ionomer has a value of around 20%. Nevertheless, even a small expansion of the layer can have a detrimental impact on its electronic conductivity. This observation indicates that, in the case of high ionomer binder content (low CBR), catalyst particles are not only covered by the polymer phase and thus insulated from each other, but are also pushed apart by the swelling and thus expanding ionomer. This explains both the increase in R_s and R_p with the decreasing value of the CBR. To verify this theory, however, it is necessary to provide independent proof of the catalyst layer properties for the different CBR values.

To provide such a proof, the electric and combined electric and ionic conductivity was determined for the catalysts themselves, as well as for the catalyst layers with different CBRs. CBRs of 50/50 and 80/20 were chosen for this purpose, as this experiment required a layer with sufficient mechanical stability. Table 1 summarises the results obtained. The electronic conductivity of the catalyst powder is relatively low, which is

Fig. 1. Equivalent electrical circuits used for the evaluation of the electrochemical impedance spectra. L [H] – inductance, R_s [Ω] – system resistivity, R_{p1}/R_{p2} [Ω] – polarisation resistances, CPE1/CPE2 – constant phase elements.

Fig. 2. Load curves of MAWE (A) using MEAs with different catalyst/binder ratios (shown in the figure inset). Geometrical area of the electrode 4 cm^2 , temperature $45 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, concentration of the liquid electrolyte concentration specified in the figure inset, electrolyte flow rate 5 ml min^{-1} . Values of R_s (B) and R_p (C) evaluated for particular MEA configurations from EIS spectra at different concentrations of KOH, temperature $45 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, maximal amplitude 10 mV , cell voltage 1.8 V , frequency range $65 \text{ kHz}-0.1 \text{ Hz}$. Cross-section of the prepared CCMs with a catalyst/binder ratio of 50/50 (D) and 93/7 (E), respectively, with a catalyst load of 2.5 mg cm^{-2} .

Table 1

Conductivity of catalyst powder, electronic and mixed conductivities (electronic + ionic) of different catalyst layers in the OH^- cycle measured in the transverse direction. Conductivity of the membrane based on the same ionomer has a value of 1.2 S m^{-1} ($30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$).

	Conductivity of catalyst powder/ S m^{-1}	Electronic conductivity/ S m^{-1}	Mixed conductivity/ S m^{-1}
NiCo ₂ O ₄ /binder 50/50	3.589	0.00031	0.76
NiCo ₂ O ₄ /binder 80/20		0.021	0.22
NiFe ₂ O ₄ /binder 50/50	0.011	0.00024	0.84
NiFe ₂ O ₄ /binder 80/20		0.00028	0.16

especially true for NiFe_2O_4 . This is due to the nature of the material. Once mixed with the non-functionalised binder, the conductivity further drops by one or more orders of magnitude. This confirms the theory

mentioned above that the catalyst particles are insulated from each other by the inert polymer binder, in this case by the inert PSEBS-CM. Once the binder is activated, and thus ionically conductive, the mixed conductivity of the layer increases significantly. Comparing the conductivity data in Table 1, it becomes obvious that the conductivity inside the catalyst layer is primarily ionic in character and is provided through anion-selective binder. Electronic contact through the catalyst phase has a value of 1–3 orders of magnitude lower and thus represents only a negligible contribution. Moreover, it is highly probable that, because of the swelling of the ionomer, the electronic contact between the catalyst particles is even further reduced compared to that between the not yet functionalised film, as discussed above. This allows one important conclusion to be drawn. An important obstacle in the CCM approach for alkaline water electrolysis is the low electronic conductivity of the catalyst phase. Thus, when utilising KOH solutions as a liquid electrolyte, the CCS approach represents an appropriate solution, since most of the catalyst particles have direct contact with the metallic structure of PTL. CCM becomes advantageous when deionised water is used as the circulating medium, which does not provide sufficient ionic contact between the electrode and the membrane separator for CCS.

It is clear that the above discussion concerning electronic contact

between the catalyst particles in the catalyst layer does not explain the important difference in the polarisation resistances determined for KOH solutions of different concentrations, see Fig. 2C. While cell Rs decrease by a factor of 2–3, Rp changes are significantly more important. The increased localisation of the electrochemical reaction close to the current feeder probably does not completely explain this behavior. It seems probable that the effect of the pH of the solution on the catalytic activity of the materials used needs to be considered. This effect has been studied previously [56]. However, this effect needs further study to understand it in more detail for the systems containing an alkaline polymer electrolyte.

For all samples studied, long-term stability was tested for up to 120 h in 10 wt.% KOH at 45 °C and with a constant load of 250 mA cm⁻². The results obtained are summarised in Fig. 3A. The highest cell voltage (lowest efficiency) was observed for the MEA with 50/50 CBR (2.209 ± 0.013 V). This is in line with the load curve experiments. On the other hand, the lowest cell voltage (highest efficiency) was achieved with 90/10 CBR (2.072 ± 0.017 V).

An important indicator for evaluating the catalyst layer stability is the increase in cell voltage over time. In the present case, this parameter was evaluated from the slope of a linear fit made from 12 points (each point used was calculated as an average of the last 60 points of the 10-h period) collected over the duration of the test. The following results were obtained: 50/50 CBR 100 μV h⁻¹, 90/10 CBR–100 μV h⁻¹ and 93/7 CBR–10 μV h⁻¹. From this result it can be concluded that, even when 90/10 CBR shows a slightly better performance, higher long-term stability indicates that the 93/7 CBR (2.110 ± 0.018 V) option is preferable from the practical application point of view. During the long-term stability test, EIS spectra were recorded at defined time intervals (see Fig. 3B,C and Fig. S8 – S13 in SI). Fluctuations in the Rs and Rp values observed during the experiment may be assigned to changes in the liquid electrolyte temperature and/or concentration. Over a time interval of 0–120 h, the Rs value increased by 4.3% for CBR 50/50. For CBRs 90/10 and 93/7, the Rs decreased by 12.0% and 11.4%, respectively. Whereas in the case of CBR 50/50 the observed Rs increase is probably caused by the compact binder damaged by the evolved gas phase, in the remaining

two cases two possible explanations are as follows. Electronic contacts between catalyst particles are renewed/established because in critical parts of the layer, the polymer binder is removed by the evolved gas phase. Since a sufficient amount of polymer electrolyte remains available in the catalyst layer, this has no impact on the ionic conductivity of the layer as such. The alternative explanation consists of gradual activation of the anion-selective phase in the catalyst layer in the course of the electrolysis by OH⁻ ions generated and transported during electrolysis.

In the case of Rp, two conclusions can be derived from the results summarised in Fig. 3C. The first is that Rp1 clearly dominates the voltage losses and thus represents the performance-determining parameter. The second concerns the stability of the catalyst. In the case of CBR 50/50 and 90/10, Rp1 tends to decrease in the first 40 h and then the value increases with time but does not outgrow the initial value. For the 93/7 CBR, Rp1 initially decreases. Afterwards it stabilises and does not change any more, indicating the good stability of the MEA.

The fact that the best performance was achieved using a MEA with the lowest amount of PSEBS-CM binder in the catalyst layer studied is because a small amount of anion-selective polymer binder improves ionic contact between the catalyst layer and the membrane separator compared to the inert binder, but at the same time it shows the lowest level of interference with the electron conductivity of the catalyst phase and product transport in the catalyst layer.

The CCMs stability may also be impacted by the layer morphology. Fig. 4 shows SEM pictures of the surfaces of MEA with CBR 93/7 prepared using an air-brush prior to and after the stability test. Both the anode and cathode layers already show an inhomogeneous surface prior to testing. Inhomogeneity can cause undesired internal tension in the catalyst layer during swelling and operation. Another aspect is the potential loss of the catalyst particles from the top of the catalyst layer. Nevertheless, morphological observation provided no proof for any of these theories. It is, however, important to bear in mind that these SEM photographs are taken in a dry state. In a swollen state the situation may differ significantly. The main outcome is, that due to the inhomogeneity of the resulting layers, an air-brush is probably not the most suitable

Fig. 3. Dependence of cell voltage (A), cell ohmic resistance (B), polarisation resistance Rp1 (C) and Rp2 (D) on time of MAWE using different MEAs (identified in the figure inset) at a current density of 250 mA cm⁻². Geometrical area of the electrode 4 cm², temperature 45 °C, concentration of the liquid electrolyte 10 wt.%, electrolyte flow rate 5 ml min⁻¹.

Fig. 4. SEM images of the surfaces of the deposited anode (top) and cathode (bottom) catalyst layers before and after the MAWE test; catalyst load 2.5 mg cm^{-2} , catalyst/binder ratio 93/7. AWE conditions: geometrical area of the electrode 4 cm^2 , temperature $45 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, different concentration of liquid electrolyte, electrolyte flow rate 5 ml min^{-1} .

method for catalyst layer deposition.

3.2. Computer-controlled ultrasonic dispersion deposition (CNC)

Once the composition of the MEA had been optimised, the catalyst layer deposition method was changed from air-brush to computer-controlled ultrasonic dispersion deposition (CNC). Fig. 5 summarises SEM pictures of the optimised MEA (93/7 CBR) as produced and after the electrolysis experiment. Compared to the catalyst layers deposited by air-brush method (see Fig. 4), both the anode and cathode layers

show a smooth and compact surface. As in the case of the air brush, no changes in the structure of the catalyst layers are visible after MEA testing under MAWE conditions, confirming its very good stability.

The performance of CNC and air-brush deposited layers is compared in Fig. 6A (for load curves for all KOH concentrations, see Fig. S14). In less concentrated KOH (1 wt.%), the CCM-MEA prepared by air brush showed a slightly better performance with current density of 82 mA cm^{-2} compared to CNC CCM-MEA (72 mA cm^{-2}) at a cell voltage of 2.0 V. EIS revealed that, at a cell voltage of 1.8 V, the resistance value assigned as R_{p1} , which represents the rate-determining step, is slightly higher for

Fig. 5. SEM images of the surfaces of the deposited anode (top) and cathode (bottom) before and after the MAWE test; catalyst load 2.5 mg cm^{-2} , catalyst/binder ratio 93/7. AWE conditions: geometrical area of the electrode 4 cm^2 , temperature $45 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, different concentration of the liquid electrolyte, electrolyte flow rate 5 ml min^{-1} .

Fig. 6. Load curves of MAWE using MEAs with optimised preparation methods (shown in the figure inset) (A). Geometrical area of the electrode 4 cm^2 , temperature $45 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, concentration of the liquid electrolyte specified in figure inset, electrolyte flow rate 5 ml min^{-1} . Values of R_s (B) and R_{p1}/R_{p2} (C) evaluated for particular MEA configurations from EIS spectra under different KOH concentrations, temperature $45 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, maximal amplitude 10 mV , cell voltage 1.8 V , frequency range $65 \text{ kHz-}0.1 \text{ Hz}$.

CNC CCM-MEA compared to air-brush CCM-MEA. For Nyquist and Bode presentations of EIS results, see Figs. S15, S16, S17, and S18. However, since the performance of the load curve is rather low for both CCM-MEAs when using a 1 wt.% KOH solution, any observed differences in current densities are not significantly pronounced and are not always easily distinguishable from the influence of dynamic variations of the

electrolyser operational conditions, such as an immediate temperature or KOH concentration.

In more concentrated KOH (15 wt.%), the CNC CCM-MEA attains 214 mA cm^{-2} , air-brush CCM-MEA only 181 mA cm^{-2} at a cell voltage of 2.0 V . The better performance is further confirmed by the EIS results (Fig. 6B and C), where CNC deposition shows lower values for all the

Fig. 7. Dependence of cell voltage (A), system resistance (B), polarisation resistance R_{p1} (C) and R_{p2} (D) on time of MAWE using different MEAs (identified in the figure inset) at a current density of 250 mA cm^{-2} . Geometrical area of the electrode 4 cm^2 , temperature $45 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, concentration of the liquid electrolyte $10 \text{ wt}\%$, electrolyte flow rate 5 ml min^{-1} . EIS spectra measured under different concentrations of KOH, temperature $45 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, maximal amplitude 10 mV , cell voltage 1.8 V , frequency range $65 \text{ kHz-}0.1 \text{ Hz}$.

resistances evaluated. With the CNC-MEA, a very homogeneous catalyst layer was achieved, improving the pathways for electric current due to the improved effective cross-sectional area. Concerning R_p , the situation is not so clear. In concentrated KOH, both CCMs showed a similar value of R_{p1} , but the air-brush prepared CCM-MEA reached a higher value of R_{p2} .

The next aspect is the stability test. As shown in Fig. 7A, in the case of the air-brush method, the average cell voltage at a current density of 250 mA cm^{-2} has a value of $2.09 \pm 0.02 \text{ V}$. The voltage increase during long-term galvanostatic electrolysis was then evaluated as $200 \mu\text{V h}^{-1}$. In contrast to this, CNC deposition showed a mean cell voltage of $2.03 \pm 0.01 \text{ V}$ and the voltage increase was as low as $1 \mu\text{V h}^{-1}$. The increase in R_s between 0 and 143 h of electrolysis was only 9% for the CNC prepared MEA, see Fig. 7B. Additionally, as follows from Fig. 6B, this increase is more due to fluctuations in R_s values, not to systematic changes in the properties of the MEA. On the other hand, the R_s of the air-brush MEA increased by 34% showing the increasing trend of the voltage. This agrees with observations made concerning the stability of an air-brush CCM-MEA. In the case of the air-brush MEA, the increase in time can also be observed for the R_p , see Fig. 7C. This effect indicates disintegration of the catalyst layer. The minor fluctuations in the R_s and R_p values are caused by the addition of water to balance its losses caused by electrolysis and by water evaporation.

In the case of CNC deposition, it can be concluded that the catalyst layer is more homogeneous, without any visible defects (Fig. 5). Moreover, dispersion of the catalyst ink by ultrasound can lead to elimination of remaining clusters of catalyst particles, which can lead to better distribution of the particles in the layer compared to the air-brush method. Due to this, very high stability of the MEA was observed during the long-term stability test. The performance in terms of current density improved by approximately 27% compared to the original composition of the MEA (93/7 CBR, air-brush method) and the voltage increase was only $1 \mu\text{V h}^{-1}$, which is the lowest increase compared to other MEAs studied in this paper. The target for efficiency (voltage) degradation is established by the FCH JU (Fuel Cells and Hydrogen Joint Undertaking) under the EU's Horizon 2020 funding programme to be $2.3 \mu\text{V h}^{-1}$ [57], which the CCM presented fully satisfies.

We further tested the MEA with different non-platinum as well as platinum catalysts in pure water. The results of this measurement can be found in Chapter 3 of SI and in Fig. S33.

Compared to the performance of MEAs using Pt catalysts achieving a current density of 214 mA cm^{-2} at 2 V in 15 wt.% KOH solution, the performance of the presented CCM MEA is rather quite low [23,30,49]. However, compared to studies dealing with catalysts based on non-platinum metals, this MEA showed a better performance of MAWE and higher long-term stability [5,28]. The performance of these MEAs can be further improved by optimising the ionomer and catalyst properties.

4. Conclusion

Using non-Pt catalysts, a stable MEA for alkaline water electrolysis was successfully prepared using a CCM technique. Chloromethylated PSEBS polymers functionalised with DABCO groups in combination with NiCo_2O_4 and NiFe_2O_4 were used for this purpose. To the best of our knowledge, this CCM is one of the first non-commercial membrane-based MEAs exhibiting a satisfactory performance and stability in an alkaline water electrolysis environment. This study has shown that limited electronic conductivity of the catalyst and especially of the deposited catalyst layer are of crucial importance. This is caused both by the low conductivity of the catalyst materials themselves and also by the internal structure of the layer, especially with regard to the impact of the ionomer binder. One solution is to use a highly active and conductive catalyst showing a satisfactory performance in very thin layers deposited on the membrane surface. Another is to apply a suitable microporous layer that provides a homogeneous distribution of the electric charge

over the catalyst layer and, at the same time, efficient removal of the gases produced. On the other hand, during stability tests, the cell voltage did not change for 140 h. This is a positive signal for future studies in the field of CCM-based MEAs. To improve the performance of the whole MAWE system, CCM with improved catalysts and a modified electrode structure need to be developed in the next step.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Michaela Plevová: Investigation, Validation, Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Jaromír Hnát:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Jan Žitka:** Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Lukáš Pavlovce:** Resources. **Miroslav Otmar:** Resources. **Karel Bouzek:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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